

Curves of accuracy rate and loss value

Beetle Data Set

(1)

Beetle Data Set

(2)

Butterfly Data Set

(3)

Butterfly Data Set

(4)

Fish Data Set

(5)

Fish Data Set

(6)

Moth Data Set

(7)

Moth Data Set

(8)